

CLINICAL-NEUROLOGICAL ASPECTS OF HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM STATE IN NEWBORNS WITH HEMORRHAGIC BRAIN LESIONS

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Abstract. Objective: To study the clinical-neurological picture and hemostasis system disorders in newborns with hemorrhagic brain lesions.

Materials and Methods: The study observed 50 newborns with intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) classified under ICD-10 codes P52.0 – P52.2. These infants were initially admitted to the intensive care unit and later transferred to the second-stage care unit for premature infants and neonatal pathology. The newborns were divided into two groups: Group 1 – preterm infants (30), Group 2 – full-term infants (30).

Results: Various prolonged laboratory alterations in the hemostasis system were found in newborns with IVH. Hypercoagulation was observed in preterm infants, while hypocoagulation was found in full-term infants. However, clinical manifestations of hemorrhagic syndrome were identified in 27% of full-term infants and in 20% of preterm infants with IVH. Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) syndrome appears to develop more frequently than it is diagnosed due to its mild and sometimes asymptomatic course.

Keywords: newborn, preterm infants, hemostasis, hypercoagulation, hypocoagulation.

The search for new approaches to improving the management of preterm infants remains a relevant issue in modern perinatology, aiming to prevent disability and reduce infant mortality. Among the conditions that worsen the prognosis for the survival and health of preterm infants, intraventricular hemorrhages (IVH; ICD-10 codes P52.0-P52.2) are highlighted [2,6]. IVH in newborns develops due to hypoxic and traumatic nervous system damage and is one of the leading causes of high perinatal mortality. One of the causes of perinatal CNS damage in newborns is chronic intrauterine hypoxia, resulting from disorders in the fetoplacental complex [9,10]. Despite numerous studies, the mechanisms of post-hypoxic cerebral pathology formation, particularly IVH, in newborns are not fully understood. Currently, immune mechanisms in the development of perinatal pathology are being actively studied [1,5,9,12].

Post-hypoxic conditions are frequently accompanied by hemostasis disorders, which can significantly aggravate the newborn's condition. The hemostasis system is a fundamental system involved in adaptation processes [7,13]. The development of hemorrhagic disorders in preterm infants can be due to anatomical and physiological characteristics, immaturity, vascular wall conditions, morphological and functional characteristics of coagulation and anticoagulation system components, and polymorphisms in genes controlling hemostasis [4,8,11]. In recent years, researchers have increasingly focused on identifying the peculiarities of gene polymorphisms controlling both vascular-platelet and plasma components of hemostasis. Understanding the phenotypic manifestations of different gene polymorphism variants holds diagnostic value for

detecting hemorrhagic disorders in infants and enables the prediction of hemostasis system disturbances [3,4].

Objective of the study: To study the clinical-neurological picture and hemostasis system disorders in newborns with hemorrhagic brain lesions.

Materials and Methods: The study observed 50 newborns with intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) classified under ICD-10 codes P52.0 – P52.2. These infants were initially admitted to the intensive care unit and later transferred to the second-stage care unit for premature infants and neonatal pathology. The newborns were divided into two groups: Group 1 – preterm infants (30), Group 2 – full-term infants (30).

Clinical-laboratory studies and neurosonography were conducted. Neurosonography was performed in real-time using transcranial ultrasound scanning of the brain according to standard sections in the frontal and sagittal planes on the SONOSCKOPESSI – 6000 device using a convex sensor of 5-7 MHz, a linear sensor of 5-10 MHz, and a sector sensor of 3-5 MHz.

Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out using Microsoft Excel 2010 and Statistica 6.1 software packages, utilizing statistical functions, Student's t-test (t), and calculating the probability of error (P).

Results and discussion. Among premature newborns, 10 were born at a gestational age of 35-37 weeks, with an average birth weight of 2790.53 g and an average body length of 48.20 cm. Six newborns were born at a gestational age of 32-34 weeks, with an average birth weight of 2027.79 g and an average body length of 42.0 cm. Fourteen were born at a gestational age of 28-31 weeks, with an average birth weight of 1582.68 g and an average body length of 39.0 cm. The second group consisted of 30 newborns born at a gestational age of 37-42 weeks. The average birth weight of these children was 3726.18 g, and the average body length was 51.5 cm.

Data on the health characteristics of the mothers of newborns with VLBW (very low birth weight) are presented in Table 1. The health status of the mothers in the group of full-term newborns was as follows: 16 mothers suffered from chronic somatic diseases – tonsillitis (6) and pyelonephritis (10). No exacerbation of chronic foci of infection was observed during pregnancy in these women. Gynecological diseases were identified in 6 women – yeast vaginitis (2) and cervical erosion (4). Sixteen mothers had pregnancy complications: 6 mothers experienced late toxemia during pregnancy, and 10 had a threat of pregnancy termination in the third trimester. Complicated deliveries were observed in 16 women.

Table 1

Characteristics of the health status of mothers of newborns

Observation group	Somatic diseases of the mother	Gynecological diseases of the mother	Pathology of pregnancy	Pathology of childbirth
I- group	20/66,6*	6/20*	24/80*	20/66,6*
II- group	16/53,3*	6/20*	16/53,3*	8/26,6*

Note: The denominator is a percentage.; *-

In 14 women of the first group, more than 2 somatic and gynecological diseases were noted. Only 6 mothers in the first group did not experience complications during pregnancy, but the severity of their children's condition was due to complications during delivery.

Among the premature newborns with VLBW (very low birth weight), there were: 16 (53.3%) from the first pregnancy, 2 (6.6%) from the second pregnancy, and 12 (40%) from the

fourth and fifth pregnancies. According to the Apgar scale, 15 (50%) children scored 7-10 points, 5 (16.6%) newborns scored 4-6 points, and 10 (33.3%) children scored 0-3 points.

Among the full-term newborns with VLBW, there were: 20 (66%) from the first pregnancy, 5 (16%) from the second pregnancy, and 5 (16%) from the fourth and fifth pregnancies. According to the Apgar scale, 5 (16%) children scored 7-10 points, 19 (63%) newborns scored 4-6 points, and 6 (20%) children scored 0-3 points.

The diagnosis of VLBW was made based on the medical history, dynamic assessment of neurological and somatic status, neurosonographic data, and lumbar puncture results. The severity of the newborns' condition was determined by neurological symptoms. Neurological disorders in the acute period were observed in 12 (40%) children with general depression, in 2 (6.6%) with hypertensive-hydrocephalic syndrome, in 4 (13.3%) with motor disorders, and in 2 (6.6%) with seizures. The combination of 3 syndromes was noted in 2 premature newborns, and the combination of 2 syndromes was noted in 4 children.

Neurological disorders in the acute period of the second group were manifested by clinical syndromes: increased neuroreflex excitability - in 14 (46.6%) newborns, general depression - in 10 (33.3%), hypertension-hydrocephalic - in 1 (3.3%), movement disorders - in 2 (6.6%) and convulsive - 2 (6.6%) children. A combination of 2 syndromes was noted in 1 newborn.

All newborns underwent an extended hemocoagulogram study and determined the main quantitative viscosity characteristics of the vascular-platelet link and coagulation link: Lee-White blood clotting time in a non-siliconized test tube, activated partial thromboplastin time, prothrombin index, blood fibrinogen and venous blood platelets. The reliability of differences for dependent and independent samples between two means was assessed using Student's t-test. Hemocoagulogram parameters were determined using generally accepted standard methods (Table 2).

Before treatment, neonates with IVH had pronounced multidirectional disorders of hemostasis parameters. At the age of 4-7 days, premature neonates with IVH with initial hypercoagulation showed clinical manifestations of hemorrhagic syndrome: melena in 4, hemorrhagic skin rashes in 4, and "coffee ground" vomiting in 6. A slight decrease in the platelet count was noted. Full-term neonates with IVH with initial hypocoagulation showed clinical manifestations of hemorrhagic syndrome: melena in 6, hemorrhagic skin rashes in 6, "coffee ground" vomiting in 4, and bleeding from injection sites in 4. Hypercoagulation, which is uncharacteristic for this period, was assessed by us as a response of the hemostasis system to IVH and hemorrhages, which is consistent with the literature data. A moderate decrease in total fibrinogen was noted. Probably, the hypocoagulation orientation of the hemostasis system in these children is associated with the depletion of the coagulation link caused by IVH, which causes an increased tendency to hemorrhagic complications, including such a dangerous one as DIC syndrome.

All newborns underwent intensive therapy, which included oxygen therapy, hypovolemia control, anticonvulsant and antibacterial therapy. Children with hemostasis disorders received antihemorrhagic therapy based on hemocoagulogram data.

Newborns with initial hypercoagulation were given antiplatelet agents, dipyridamole, trental, euphyllin, vitamin E. Heparin was used at a dose of 10-15 U/kg, mainly for flushing catheters. Therapy for newborns with IVH with initial hypocoagulation included, first of all,

transfusion of fresh frozen plasma at an average rate of 10 ml/kg intravenously in order to replenish the deficiency of procoagulants, anticoagulants, fibrinolysins.

Table 2

Coagulogram indicators in newborns

Hemocoagulogram indicator	4-7 days		8-15 days		16-28 days	
	Group I (n=30)	Group II (n=30)	Group I (n=30)	Group II (n=30)	Group I (n=30)	Group II (n=30)
Lee-White blood clotting time	5,2 ± 0,1	14,5±0,22	7,5±0,4	8,3±0,2	9,3±0,18	10,8± 0,3
Activated partial thromboplastin time	30,4±0,33	38,2±0,4	34,7±0,9	39,6±0,7	36,2±0,45	37,7±0,6
Prothrombin index	88±2,6	53±3,4	82±5,2	63±4,6	80±5,6	82,7±3,7
Total fibrinogen	3,98±0,2	1,52±0,1	3,34±0,09	2,3±0,08	2,49±0,2	3,3±0,2
Platelets	258±6,1	278±1,41	244,8±4,6	245,7±4,6	228,3±6,55	237±4,3

Against the background of the treatment at the age of 8-15 days, no critical indicators were noted in the hemocoagulogram of newborns in both groups. However, there was a tendency for the number of platelets to decrease. The revealed hemorrhagic manifestations in the clinical status of newborns in this period were manifested by insignificant hemorrhagic syndrome: melena - in 2, hemorrhagic rashes on the skin - in 3, leveled off, and new ones were not noted. In full-term newborns, clinical hemorrhagic manifestations were not noted during this period. The tendency for normalization of hemostasis parameters in all groups occurred by the end of the 16-28th day of life. However, the level of platelet count remained at low standard values.

Conclusion. Treatment aimed at correcting disorders in the hemostasis system was carried out in the neonatal intensive care unit and the second stage of premature care unit for 10-15 days and neonatal pathology.

Thus, neonates with IVH were found to have multidirectional long-term laboratory changes in the hemostasis system. Hypercoagulation was observed in premature infants, hypocoagulation - in full-term neonates. However, clinical manifestations of hemorrhagic syndrome in neonates with IVH are detected in full-term infants - 27%, and in premature infants in 20% of cases. Obviously, DIC syndrome develops much more often than is diagnosed due to its poorly expressed and even asymptomatic course.

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